

Craft Histories, Textile Futures: The Emotional Affectivity of a Quilt...

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Abstract

From Marge Simpson's family quilt to my Northern Irish paternal grandmother's patchworks; from 19th century US homesteaders to rural Ulster farmers; from traditional salvage frugality to the new eco-sustainability; from poly-cotton duvets washable at 40° to 'smart' and intelligent textile technology...my paper examines the emotionally-rich content captured in the fabrication, materiality and design of textile quilts, and indicate how their combinations of cerebral and 'felt' substance and affect provides a template for emotionally meaningful textile design within a 'craft futures' scenario.

Functional, utilitarian and decorative, quilts mark the commonplace rituals and universal emotions of bed, and the momentous and miniscule events and significations of life. Those quilts are embedded with human experience, an interface where a human subject performatively meets and merges with a designed object.

Conventionally, the future for textile design is described as hi-tech / 'smart' (wearable computers, bio-mimetic fibres, electronic and digital fabrics, geo-textiles, engineering textile composites...) and 'eco' (sustainable, biodegradable, recyclable processes and products). Where does emotional design fit in?

My paper advocates a fresh examination of the very particular traditions, characteristics, processes and outcomes of hand-crafted, fabric-salvaged, highly-functional, labour-intensive, emotionally-invested, collectively-stitched, pre-industrial, domestic quilts both in the US and in my family. I will indicate how those aesthetics and materialities might allow a redefinition of 'textile design futures'. I will disclose one practical aspect of my vision of how technological textile innovations and advances might allow emotionally-rich, quality-measurable, poetically-valuable designed future living.

Keywords: memory, quilt, fabric, textile technology, scraps, salvage, signification, narrative, history, home-spun, function, puritan, craft, utilitarian, pre-industrial, myth, domestic, colonising, tradition, feminine, thrift, metaphor, meaning, smart, intelligent, experience, stories, comfort, affectivity, conceptual, material, magic, genealogy, hand-work, time-investment, contemporary, electro-technology, e-broidery, conductive circuitry, wireless, communication, temperature-sensitive, micro-electronic, light-emission, optical, nanotechnology, shape-memory alloys, digital, sensory, tactile, artefact, ritual, poetic, thermochromic, hybrid, engineered, performative, interface

Maternal memory

When Bart Simpson's dog shredded up the Bouvier family quilt, his mother Marge (née Bouvier) was more than upset. "Six generations, ruined!" she screamed

(www.headworks.net)... The Simpsons are arguably us at our all-consuming best, so why Marge's trauma at the loss of an old bit of fabric?

When my childhood dog gave birth to seven pups on my father's mother's quilt, my own mother was less disturbed. She burnt it, and bought me a duvet with a poly-cotton cover. In 1975, that was my mother's 'visible textile technology, machine-washable at 40°...

My grandmother's quilt was neither skilfully made nor especially beautiful. Compared to the fine white-on-white embroidery of my *mother's* mother, this was a poor 'country' thing, a thin textile sandwich of bought striped ticking, two grey woollen blankets, and a top covering of irregularly pieced patchings of patterned cotton. Because my grandmother wasn't given to 'idle chat', my father named each fabric scrap as the Sunday 'bests', working shirts, and dance dresses of his sisters – "there's Alice, there's Lily, there's Eileen"... As a child I couldn't match the flowers, checks and stripes of the fabric scraps with the youthful histories of my staid and serious aunts... I'm working here with a methodology that insists on the readability of cloth through memory, familiar signification, narrative and a kind of 'low history'. It references a range of writers including Pennina Barnett, Sarat Maharaj, Lucy Lippard, Elaine Showalter, Rozsika Parker, Pamela Johnston, etc. Connected to that, I strategically use a discursive and creative writing methodology in order to performatively 'act out' the implications of my analysis of historical objects, and my usage of them to 'futureground' my own design development.

My grandmother's was an 'Ulster utility quilt' (Wilson, 2002), evidence of a 'make do and mend' salvage mentality necessary in working class Ulster homes in the early part of the 20th century (Ulster refers to the Northern quarter of Ireland, comprising today's Northern Ireland plus three additional counties which remained part of the independently-governed Irish Free State - Eire - following partition of Ireland in 1921. Since my paternal grandparents were Protestant, the term 'Ulster' was frequently used interchangeably, if incorrectly, with 'Northern Ireland' to indicate allegiance to the British crown. I use it here in a kind of nostalgia for the simplicity of their formulaic political thinking). (Figure 1).

Figure 1, Utility quilt, Ulster, c. 1900

It links cross-historically with so-called ‘britches’ quilts of impoverished and slave communities in 19th century US America (Suit, 2004), and similar ‘frontier-spirit’, home-spun utility textiles created by working class immigrants to Australia (Harper, 2001).

Unlike many women of that class and time in the North-West part of Ireland, my grandmother was not involved in the massive shirt-making concerns which had begun particularly in Derry City in the 19th century, and which linger (in travail) in a city of great unemployment and political strife until today (Gavin, 2001). Where many women worked either in the factories or as outworkers, augmenting their shirt-making income (with its supply of surplus fabric scraps) by making and selling patchwork quilts, my grandmother was a small-farmer in an isolated and barren valley in rural County Derry.

Maggie Harper (née McCully) rode a horse, gathered ‘purdies’ (potatoes) from their drills, snared hares, reared five children to adulthood, claimed a usable field from a bog, walked and worked ‘like a man’. She went miles to worship her god, and boiled pins to ward off the ‘evil eye’. A stoical and undemonstrative woman, her sewing – like her farming - lacked finesse or superfluity. It was done with as much care as was necessary to create a functional bed-covering, no more and no less...

I’d like to say my grandmother gave me my love of textiles and my desire for stitch. But she didn’t. Yet, the memory of the undecorated not-so-great quilt she made is strangely affective. It speaks to me of more than six generations of Scots-Irish puritan stock, a genealogy of work ethic, plain fare, simple ways, hard graft, muddled with the coarse and fearful superstition of country folk. This emotive heady mix is *my* genealogy and I have grown to accept it...

Coarse craft

My paternal grandmother's quilt was the 'bad craft', yet functional, equivalent of my other grandmother's careful decorative embroidery. The latter epitomised the combination of great technical skill, particular care, and detailed design unique to specific and arguably privileged understandings 'craft' (Leonard, 2003; Watney, 1997; Greenhalgh, 1997). The former typified an alternative (historical) crafting concerned simply with "producing objects that were necessary to life" (Smith, 1986) or indeed "doing well [enough] that which is required" (Johnson, 2000). The quilt introduced above was fundamentally the result of a hand process creating an essentially utilitarian craft object (Lucie-Smith, 1981). To leave its definition at that, however, would be to negate the key emotional content which it carried forward to now from its time of primary use...

The 'bad craft' unruly sewing and irregular patching of the quilt is a signifier, for me, of my grandmother's ambiguous status as a woman. Where her rural counterparts were finding finesse in the flourishing shirt-factories, she salvaged and held her tiny farm on a rocky hillside... Jefferies talks of the "rebellious 'crazy fields' ... transgressive breaches... Multiple peaks of fluid stitches, rhythmical passes of woven lines" of critically strenuous textile practices (Jefferies, 1995), and this is the territory inhabited by my grandmother's ghost....

Jonathan Holstein, writing of 18th and 19th century US quilts, locates them as:

tokens of our pre-industrial past, the homestead which exists in fact or myth, and the hand skills which our ancestors practiced as a matter of course, symbolic of household industry (Holstein, 1975).

His words are densely packed, and I begin my unravelling of their meaning with his allusion to the 'homestead'.

Clockwise from top left
Figure 2, Cactus Basket quilt, Kentucky USA, 1860-90
Figure 3, Dresden Plate quilt, Kentucky USA, 1870
Figure 4, Barn Raising Log Cabin quilt, Kentucky USA, 1900
Figure 5, Lone Star quilt, Kentucky USA, 1930

Long before the exquisitely beautiful hand-crafted quilts of settled US white communities were made (Figures 2-5), women and men - immigrants from Ireland and the rest of Europe - shifted their families painstakingly across an unforgiving and unfamiliar ‘new land of opportunity’. Such women made utility quilts “as fast as [they] could so [their] famil[ies] wouldn’t freeze...and as beautiful as [they] could so [their] heart[s] wouldn’t break” (Chase, 1976). Before the notion of ‘home’ as an interior domestic space for “household industry” was established in the log cabins of ‘new’ Americans, *homesteads* were literally carved out (salvaged) [colonised] as patches of land stitched together by pioneering will. The mythic or actual pioneers/colonists of Holstein’s study activate, for me, my grandmother’s hard existence, and the uncompromising functionality of her roughly sewn quilt...

My grandmother inhabited ‘ambiguous spaces’: the historically masculine external property of her field; the interior domestic space that Holstein later ascribes to the ‘traditional feminine’ (Holstein, 1975). The “household industry” symbolised above by hand-making was only *part* of my grandmother’s remit and not her primary drive. I read her ‘half-handed’ stitches as indicative of her partial habitation only of the territory and emotional space of ‘women’s work’.

In the film *How to Make an American Quilt* (1995) women of three generations work collectively to both create a traditional marriage quilt and confirm the central youngest character in the traditions of her 'feminine role'. The protagonist's ambiguity around her 'feminine destiny' is gradually dispelled as the quilt and its metaphors take shape throughout the film's narrative. The quilt in the film is a formidable contemporary example of a particular kind of Pennsylvania traditional album quilt (Figure 6), and it is highly symbolic of the 'good craft' associated with 'successful womanliness'. That is, the balance, intricacy and care manifest in such a quilt becomes what Holstein urges is a "visible expression...of culturally valued feminine virtues of thrift, industry, application, care of the home" (Holstein, 1975).

Figure 6, Pineapple Friendship Appliqué with Vase and Vine Border quilt, Pennsylvania US, 1850-60

References to the practices of collecting, salvaging and hoarding of "scraps of lace, labels, chintz, gingham, and other feminine paraphernalia" and "traditional craft techniques associated with women such as cutting, sewing, piecing, hooking, quilting, and appliqué" are common (Constantine, 1997). Indeed Lippard (1983) asserts the quilt as the "prime visual metaphor for women's lives, women's culture". Such references are frequently and variously problematised, utilised, and complexified a range of texts in respect of essentialisms and definitions of femininity, domesticity and textiles (Parker, 1984; Munro, 1999; Jefferies, 1995; Aitken, 1999). Just as Parker (1984) asserts the duality of, for example, embroidery in terms of both its inculcation of femininity in women and its enabling of a negotiation of its constraints, I will argue for my grandmother's use of so-called 'badly crafted' stitching to

both indicate her ‘double-gendered’ employment in home and on farm, and express her misgivings (if not her fury) at its demands on her (Jefferies, 1996).

Further, I might argue that the “salvage art” (Holstein, 1975) of hand-sewing bed-coverings was of little excitement compared to the salvage of a strip of field from a barren bog, a sick calf from its early death, or a potato crop from the ever-present threat of blight. Rather than being of ‘traditional feminine’ stock, my grandmother’s quilt is both a signifier of her feminine ambiguity...and, nevertheless, a symbol by its very presence of her commitment to ‘Six generations, saved’!

Yet, that is not to ignore the more typical contemporary readings and significations of historical and traditional quilts. Holstein again asks us to consider the time-value of labour-investment in the meticulous piecing of fabric scraps. He writes of “the hand-based skills of an earlier, more stable and static time...[as] ...perhaps more meaningful emotionally as relics of a ‘simpler’ age” (Holstein, 1975).

While he speaks of this emotional content in relation to the speed of impersonal production in the industrial age, this paper seeks to consider how developments in ‘smart’, and ‘intelligent’ technical textiles also ‘fit’ with a simpler, slower, emotionally meaningful sensibility.

Beds and blankets

Functional, utilitarian and decorative, traditional quilts mark the commonplace rituals and universal emotions of bed (sex, death, birth, sleep, comfort, warmth, nurture...), and the momentous and miniscule events and significations of life. Recurrent motifs in traditional US quilts include, for example, wedding rings, drunken walks, ‘women’s work’, regional symbols, architectural signs (www.americanquilts.com). Such quilts are embedded – in their composition, design, image content, and in their bodily usage – with human emotions, operating as textile interfaces where human subjects performatively meet/merge with designed objects. If cloth itself is in some fundamental way a container of human experience (Barnett, 1999), and thread a “malleable transmitter of ideas” (Johnson, 2000), they are co-joined in a quilt to extremely powerful effect...

Contemporary examples of quilts of great emotional significance are numerous and varied. British artist Tracey Emin memorably gave us her bed (Figure 7), and told us who she'd slept with (Figure 8).

Figure 7, Tracey Emin *My Bed* 1998-99

Figure 8, Tracey Emin *Everyone I Have Ever Slept With (1963-1995)* 1995

© the artist

Photo credit: Stephen White Courtesy Jay Jopling/White Cube (London)

No shy seamstress, however, it is her appliquéd blankets that tell us the stories of that bed (Figure 9), and the love, sex, and death that gets sited there... (Constantine/Reuter, 1997).

Figure 9, Tracey Emin *Automatic Orgasm* 2001 © the artist

Photo credit: Stephen White
Courtesy Jay Jopling/White Cube (London)

The NAMES Project showed by its massive scale, its tiny personal detail, and its use of the quilt-sign of comfort (Figure 10), how monumentally devastating the AIDS pandemic was and continues to be (Epstein/Friedman, 1989).

Figure 10, The NAMES Project AIDS Memorial Quilt (ongoing since 1987)
Figure 11, Faith Ringgold *Echoes of Harlem* 1980 © the artist

Faith Ringgold’s quilted and sewn pictures of her family and neighbours in Harlem (Figure 11) echo with the lived experiences expressed in quilts made by North American former slaves like Harriet Powers (Figure 12) (Fry, 2002).

Figure 11, Harriet Powers (1837-1911) *Untitled Quilt*

Sarat Maharaj reminds us that the quilt’s emotional affectivity lies in its duality, its ability to be simultaneously a “domestic commodity” and “conceptual device”... With all other meanings intact, the quilt remains for him – and in the examples above - inextricably bound, even obliquely, to “the notion of wrapping up, keeping warm, sleep and comfort, some feeling of hearth and home”.

Material magic

I have proposed the quilt as variously a symbol of genealogical history, a memory container, a warm covering, a troubled signifier of gender, an example of hard hand-work and time-investment, a well- or poorly-crafted object, a token of domesticity, and ultimately an emotionally affective textile. What then of the correspondence between the fabric scraps of Sunday 'bests', working shirts and skirts, and dance dresses of my aunts in my grandmother's quilt and contemporary textiles?

'Smart' and 'intelligent' fabrics are now almost ubiquitous as massive shifts forward in textile (and other) technologies provide us with fabric/fibre scenarios our grandmothers would not have dreamt of (Kettley, 2002; Mann, 2000), eclipsing a poly-cotton duvet, machine-washable at 40° ...

Philips' woven and stitched electro-technology...

MIT Media Lab 'E-broider' conductive circuitry (Post, 2000)...

Hussein Chalayan's remote-control dress...

Levis' seamless, wireless entertainment and communications jackets... (Figure 13)...

Wearable fabric-embedded mobile phone/camera technology (Trialdi, 1999;

Schrooten, 1998; Noble, 2000; Steinberger, 2002)...

Fabric antennae, radio tagged cloths, SoftSwitch...(Borglow, 1994)...

Infineon Technologies' temperature-sensitive and micro-electronic light-emission fabrics (Figure 14)...

Georgia Tech' optical fibres to detect military damage and transmit location data (Georgia Tech, 1996; Duakantas, 2001, Spectrum 2000, Koshima, 2000)...

Nanotechnology 'spider-silk' (www.netcomposites.com)...

IBM's shape(drape)-memory alloys...

Figure 13, Levis / Philips Jacket

Figure 14, Maggie Orth, Emily Cooper and Derek Lockwood *Firefly Dress*

Smith (2004) articulated the problematics of these textile scenarios - especially to textile designer-makers interested in 'craft' - noting the tendency to think oppositionally, pitting 'hand' against 'digital', sensory versus rational, tactile facing technological, 'flawed' opposing 'perfect', even human contrasting with machine... My project is concerned with finding how and where 'smart', and 'intelligent' technological textiles maintain and celebrate the simpler, slower, emotionally meaningful sensibility....

Human culture, cloth and craft are inextricably linked to myth, artefact, magic, and ritual (Seelig, 2003), and the potential for new textile processes and materials to surprise and delight must not be overlooked in the race to solve perceived problems of efficiency, power, communication, reliability, connectivity, intelligence, security, control, etc. (Gershman, 2000). Concerns are already noted in respect of health, social, privacy implications of the ubiquity of electro-technology (Batista, 2001; Bois, 2001; Borglow, 1994; Slaton, 2001), and Kettley asserts that "...in the future, harmonising and humanizing the technological world will be the ultimate challenge" (Kettley, 2002).

Professor Kevin Warwick (Head of Cybernetics, Reading University, UK) is examining 'downloading' and 'storing' human emotions as electrical impulses (Wakefield 2001), Picard (2000) seeks the emotion in technological advance, and McCullough (1998) argues to uphold

“humane traits and values during the formative stages of new practices in digital media”. These are evidence of a search for something more ‘felt’ than *cool efficient technology* or *chemical ‘magic tricks’*.

Figure 15, Hella Jongerius *Mobile Dreaming* 2001
Figure 16, Rachel Wingfield *Digital Dawn Blind* 2003

Designers like Hella Jongerius (Figure 15) and Rachel Wingfield (Figure 16) seem to manage this, and my wider *Craftfutures* project (www.craftfutures.co.uk) specifically advocates a fresh examination of the very particular traditions, characteristics, processes and outcomes of hand-crafted, fabric-salvaged, highly-functional, labour-intensive, emotionally-invested, collectively-stitched, pre-industrial, domestic, 19th century Ulster / US / Australian (it has to be said...colonialist / impoverished / enslaved) quilts, working towards a vision of how technological textile innovations and advances might allow emotionally-rich, quality-measurable, poetically-valuable designed future living.

Blush...

In 2000, I was commissioned to create a permanent artwork for the new Women’s Centre, Derry. My work – *Heart* – is a rose pink Canadian smocked velvet cotton ceiling in the Library of the new building. The work was exactly tailored to the room’s dimensions and was laboriously hand-stitched in conscious and performative reference to women’s historical and time-consuming labour, to Derry’s historical textile industries, and to my grandmother’s quilt...

Now, in 2004, I have returned to Canadian smocking, piecing and patching, snipping and snatching, in my *craftfutures* project. I have embarked on the creation of a series of ‘hybrid quilts’ using a cross-disciplinary approach to traditional hand-stitching, patterning, and the processes / products of technological textile advances. In the range of quilts (the first being exhibited at m-e-s-h, Seven Seven Gallery, London in April 2004), I variously work with innovative electronic engineering, fabric electro-conductivity, digital and thermochromic fabric printing, laser-cut-cutting and ultrasonic welding.

My current offering to a concept of ‘engineered emotion’, however, is a textile ‘quilt’ called *Blush* (Figure 17).

Figure 17, Catherine Harper Mock-up for *Blush* 2004

My grandmother’s thin and irregular quilt covering my narrow childhood bed. A functional ‘utility quilt’ (Wilson, 2002), it evidenced frugality, salvage, isolation, Puritanism, stoicism, and lacked finesse, decoration or pleasure. It was highly invested with her tough and hard emotions...

But, as I have alluded, the bed is a site of sexual passion, procreative delight, coy amusement, and sleepy pleasures...and a blushing cheek is symptomatic of them all. *Blush* is time-invested and meticulous, representative of my emotional engagement through the seductive pleasure of skilled making, focussed crafting and traditional technical expertise. The creation of emotional meaning then allows space for the intervention of a technical textile product – thermochromic ink. The velvet fabric used is over-dyed with thermochromic ink, and the changing temperature provided by a thermostat-operated heat-pad on the reverse of the quilt. Hence, the work appears uniformly cream and white, and at random intervals it is suffused with a pink glow integral to its very fibre. That is, the quilt itself – its actual fibres – blushes...

Blush is functional, but its function is shifted from that of the bed-covering providing protection, warmth and privacy, to a 'conceptual function' concerned with both expressing and eliciting an emotional and technologically exciting affect (Boutrup, 2004). It is therefore created and offered as a performative interface between an emotional human subject and an emotionally-designed, emotionally-signifying object. *Blush* exactly activates Maharaj's 'quilt duality' wherein the quilt operates as both "domestic commodity" and "conceptual device" (Maharaj, 2001). My grandmother would both recognise it and never have dreamt of it... Certainly, I propose that the surprise and delight the blushing quilt activates goes some way to "harmonising and humanizing the technological world" (Kettley, 2002) in a helpful and tender way which is richly emotional, of measurable quality, and of poetic value...

Futureground? A hard field, echoing generations back, washable at 40°... a bit emotional, and a bit magic...

Credits

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